

Plan for the dissemination and exploitation of results including communication activities

Project title: **Enhancing Research and Innovation Synergies for Schools of Economics and Business**

Project no. 101159106 — RIS4SEB

D5.1 Plan for the dissemination and exploitation of results (due in M6), to be updated in M15 and 36

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Work package: WP5 Dissemination, communication and exploitation of results

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Executive summary

This Plan for the dissemination and exploitation of results including communication activities (or PEDR for short) is a living and foundational guide for RIS4SEB's communicational activities. It focuses on creating momentum for the project's outputs (communication), **fostering interest by a multitude of stakeholders and identifying channels to share the project's results** and findings (dissemination) and in terms of the use of the outputs (exploitation).

More broadly, the plan covers the **project's target groups, brand identity, dissemination and communication tools and channels**, community building and engagement strategies, and planning and monitoring mechanisms. The PEDR will also be updated during the RIS4SEB project, in M15, and at the end of the project, in M36.

Main points to take away from this PEDR:

- ✓ The main target groups for communication in the RIS4SEB project are **researchers, research managers and management of institutions**.
- ✓ The **acronym RIS4SEB** should always be used in communication of the project.
- ✓ The defined colors for use in the online environment are **#FFAB9B, #F5C7B5, #F7D6C9, #595959 and #000000**.
- ✓ **A PowerPoint presentation** in the project's unified style should be used for consistent visual communication.
- ✓ Any publication or material prepared shall display **the project logo, EU flag and funding statement**.
- ✓ All current information and outputs from the project will be available for download on the **project's website** and the project profile on the **Zenodo platform**.
- ✓ Information about the current steps and outputs of the project will be shared through the project's **social media profiles (LinkedIn and X)**.
- ✓ **EARMA conference** will serve as dissemination multipliers and source of feedback mid-project.
- ✓ **A final conference** will be organized to promote the project results and experiences to scale up the effects of the project.

1. Introduction

1.1 About RIS4SEB project

RIS4SEB is a Horizon Europe project set out to strengthen synergies between non-centrally managed programmes and centrally managed programmes. The Pathway to synergies initiative allows us to capitalize on the know-how the partners already created under the non-centrally managed programmes, such as ERDF or Interreg, and to apply this knowledge on research international programmes, such as Horizon Europe, and **firmly establish ourselves on the European Research Area map.**

The RIS4SEB project creates a synergy for the widening project partners (Prague University of Economics and Business, Kaunas University of Technology, and Estonian Business School) who were previously successful in obtaining ERDF, Interreg, or similar indirect EU projects in cooperation with a highly experienced non-widening partner, the Bocconi University, building a pathway towards **increased success in international research projects such as within the Horizon Europe program.** To this end, based on an analysis of widening countries low integration into ERA, the consortium chooses to focus on the research areas of economics and business, with the project partners all being either economics and business universities or schools / faculties.

The project overall objective is to design and pilot three strategies aiming at enabling and facilitating effective synergies between Horizon Europe and other national/regional funds, by **strengthening Internationalization of R&I widening actors, developing Human Resources, and improving Research management capacity and overall competitiveness of the widening partners.** RIS4SEB will achieve this objective via supplementary capacity-building activities, such as networks analysis, sharing of infrastructures, upskilling of research managers and researchers and research proposal pipelines and clinics, resulting in submitting of at least 4 joint Horizon Europe projects.

The RIS4SEB project began on June 1, 2024, and is scheduled to run for 3 years. By the end, the project will develop policy recommendations to ensure that the gained knowledge is distributed to and openly shared with regional and national Managing Authorities of EU programs to foster synergies among the many different funding programs.

1.2 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Objectives

The broken-down objectives of the plan are as follows:

- To disseminate the project results **among researchers, experts, and other shareholders** but also communicating the achievements **to the public.**
- To develop and continuously update the Plan for the dissemination and exploitation of results including **communication activities.**
- To carry out **the final project conference**, openly sharing the gained knowledge and insight with external widening Economics and Business schools, including the policy recommendations set to be developed by the end of the project.

2. Target Groups

The aim of disseminating project results is to share the developed knowledge and results with an identified set of target groups in order for them **to benefit from the results, exploit them, or even provide feedback for the consortium** to integrate in further activities.

2.1 Primary target groups

The identified intra-consortium target groups are:

- **Researchers in the partner institutions.** This group will be the primary beneficiaries of the project results. They will be trained in proposal writing and they will pilot their upgraded capabilities through writing new Horizon Europe project proposals still during RIS4SEB's duration.
- **Research managers.** This group will be implementing the developed strategies, therefore exploiting the results. Additionally, they will be trained in Work package 3 (Improved HR strategy and development of transferable skills) and therefore constitute a direct beneficiary of the project activities.
- **Management of institutions.** This group will be consulted throughout the project (either through involvement in the Advisory Board or particular problem-solving groups) to ensure smooth implementation of the developed strategies.

All 3 target groups mentioned above will be directly involved in preparation of strategies developed by this project, thus maximizing the buy-in and acceptance of the resulting change.

2.2 Additional target groups

Additional important target groups are:

- **National and regional Managing Authorities** responsible for ERDF, ESF, cohesion funds, and other research programmes: the consortium identified relevant actors responsible for the design and implementation of the various research and / or development programmes. They will be invited **to take part in RIS4SEB's Advisory Board** in order to allow for a maximum co-creation process of the three cornerstone strategies.
- **EU institutions**, in particular the DG Region, and DG RTD: similarly, representatives of DG Regio and DG RTD will be invited to RIS4SEB's Advisory Board.
- **Associations of Universities and Businesses (in widening countries):** namely, KTU provides direct link with the ECIS (The European Consortium of Innovative Universities), VSE is part of strategic alliances of CEMS (Global Alliance in Management Education), AACSB (Association to Advance Collegiate Schools of Business) and PIM (Partnership in International Management). The associations will be addressed as dissemination multipliers.
- **EARMA**, and in the case of the Czech Republic, **CZARMA**, will be used not only as **communication platforms**, but also as **feedback providers**.
- **Representatives of Economics and Business schools** in the widening countries. RIS4SEB plans on creating an online interactive community of Economics and Business school representatives. They will be contacted and invited to the **final conference** where the consortium will share its lessons learned and findings about integrating into the ERA.

Specifically, the consortium plans on inviting **representatives of widening schools** which are featured in the Financial Times European Business School Rankings 2022, such as Nova School of Business and Economics (PT), Católica Lisbon School of Business and Economics (PT), Koç University Graduate School of Business (TR), Kozminski University (PL), or the University of Ljubljana, School of Economics and Business (SI). These universities are supposedly in a similar position with excellent higher education performance and limited research internationalization. However, other widening economics and business schools are to be invited as well, for instance, University of Economics in Bratislava (SL) or the Athens University of Economics and Business (GR), who are partner universities of the coordinator. Still, the consortium plans on sharing the invitation through all the available channels so that the project results and findings can be shared widely and openly.

- **Networks of National Contact Points** will be invited to help identify suitable funding opportunities and they will be consulted with the development of the policy recommendations. Finally, National Contact Points can act as **dissemination multipliers** in the partner countries and in the EU.
- **Other projects funded under the pilot Pathways to synergies call**, especially those delivering the upstream synergy, will be invited to partake in the **online community to provide mutual feedback and serve as information multipliers**.

3. Project Identity and Templates

3.1 Name and Description

The project's official name is **Enhancing Research & Innovation Synergies for Schools of Economics and Business (RIS4SEB)**. The acronym of the project should always be used in Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation activities. RIS4SEB must be written in capital letters (upper case). It should not be stated as “Ris4seb” or “ris4seb”.

3.2 Project logo

The logo is available in colour, white (to be used for certain coloured backgrounds) and grayscale in JPEG, PNG, PDF formats. The logo should always appear fully intact regardless of its size - it must never be stretched, altered or distorted.

The official project documents use the logo and the full project name:

On social media, it is possible to use only the rectangle symbol from the logo:

3.3 Project colours

RIS4SEB’s colours should always be used to ensure a homogenous brand identity. Their use and specifications are indicated in the Table 1:

Table 1: RIS4SEB colour scheme

CMYK colour for print	RGB colour for online	HEX colour for online
0/33/41/0	rgb(255, 171, 155)	#FFAB9B
4/22/29/0	rgb(245, 199, 181)	#F5C7B5
3/16/21/0	rgb(247, 214, 201)	#F7D6C9
100/100/100/1000	rgb(0, 0, 0)	#000000
0/0/0/65	rgb(89, 89, 89)	#595959

3.4 Project templates

For consistent visual communication, it is necessary to use PowerPoint and Word templates in the project's unified style: [Visual style, logos and templates](#).

3.5 Disclaimer and Visual Identity Notices

All RIS4SEB communication activities **must systematically acknowledge EU funding**. This includes media relations, information material including factsheets and presentations, posters, brochures, social media posts, and more. To do so, please always include:

- The EU emblem that acknowledges funding: [download an official version](#).

Funded by the
European Union

- The following statement: “Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

3.6 Disclaimer Check List: Do’s and Don’ts

- ✓ Always make sure the EU emblem has **appropriate prominence** when displayed with other logos (at least the same size as the biggest logo).
- ✓ Do not use underlined text, italic or font effects in the funding statement, and use a black, white or blue (EU flag colour) font depending on the background.
- ✓ The funding statement can be translated into a local language, where appropriate.
- ✓ The statement “Funded by the European Union” or “Co-funded by the European Union” must always be spelt out in full and placed next to the emblem.

Any publication or material prepared by the consortium members, even if at the national level, shall at least display the project logo and EU flag and funding statement. This includes material done on behalf of RIS4SEB and in the framework of the tasks assigned in the project to the partners.

4. Dissemination and Communication Tools

4.1 Website

[RIS4SEB's website](#) was launched in September 2024 and is the **project's central online repository**. It outlines the project's mission, consortium members, as well as work packages and achieved milestones and goals. The website also congregates the latest news items, upcoming and past events, and contact details.

4.2 Press releases

At the start of the project, both an [English](#) and [Czech](#) press release was published online and shared on the project's social media accounts. We will continue to inform about other **significant milestones** through press releases, both on the RIS4SEB's website and on other media and social networks.

4.3 Social media

Social media is key for the project's communication and dissemination success. It is a quick and direct way to engage a wide external and targeted audience. [X](#) and [LinkedIn](#) are RIS4SEB's main social media channels. We will focus on **quick and instantaneous updates on the project**, sharing concise project results, photographs, and tagging partners and relevant EU bodies.

In addition, it will be a space to easily **share tagged mentions of the project by partners and collaborators**. The latter, LinkedIn, will feature similar content but with a broader and longer scope in a more professional environment.

The following labels and hashtags will also be used on social media:

- X: @REA_research @EUgreenresearch @HorizonEU
- LinkedIn: @European Research Executive Agency @EU Science, Research and Innovation

4.4 Zenodo

Since Zenodo has become a recognized online platform **for sharing and promoting research project outcomes on an international scale**, we will also utilize it for the RIS4SEB project. We will actively present our results in the Upload section, and through the dedicated [profile of our RIS4SEB research project](#).

This profile will feature not only the outcomes of our work but also for **event invitation to the Final conference**, as mentioned below. Zenodo's open-access and collaborative approach will ensure broad visibility and engagement with the research community.

5. Community Building and Engagement

5.1 EARMA conference

Key project results along with the project’s progress will be shared through the **EARMA community**. Additionally, Czechia features a national version of [EARMA](#), [CZARMA](#), of which the coordinators of this project are members. EARMA and CZARMA will serve not only as dissemination multipliers, but also sources of **feedback mid-project**. It is expected that the conference will take place in Spring 2026 (in April or May, as usual).

5.2 Final conference

A **final conference** will be organized in hybrid mode and jointly with the final end-of-project meeting in Prague at VSE. Representatives from outside of the project from economics and business schools and universities from widening Economics and Business schools will be invited to listen to the **project results and experiences to scale up the effects of the project**. A final conference will be held in May 2027.

Picture 1: Task responsibilities for dissemination and exploitation

TASK NUMBER	TASK TITLE	TASK LEADER
WP5	Dissemination, communication, and exploitation of results	VSE
T5.1	DEC Plan	VSE
T5.2	Website and social media	VSE
T5.3	EARMA conference	VSE
T5.4	Conference for econ and business schools	KTU

6. Exploitation

6.1 Exploitation plan

The whole consortium will exploit RIS4SEB’s results both during and after project completion. Firstly, Joint internationalization strategy for R&I will be developed during the first half of the project and immediately capitalized on by the project partners through its implementation into the respective institutional strategic documents. **Successful implementation of the Joint internationalization strategy for R&I will significantly contribute to the generation of the expected outcomes**, and ultimately to the overall success of this project.

HR strategy will be similarly fully exploited during project duration. If properly carried out, the upskilling of research managers and researchers will serve as a cornerstone of the widening partners’ journey into ERA. The HR strategy will be piloted immediately alongside research management strategy. Combined, they will **result in four new competitive international research project proposals**. Except for the immediate results of an efficient research management environment and new project proposals, we expect **positive externalities in the form of new professional contacts and links created throughout this project**. Ideally, this will lead to a multiplication effect of RIS4SEB’s results.

The consortium plans on openly sharing the results, the gained knowledge and findings so that external actors can take them up for their own exploitation and potential benefit.

Table 2 Overview of planned exploitation activities and deliverables

<i>Deliverable number</i>	<i>Deliverable task</i>	<i>Due date</i>
<i>D1.2</i>	<i>Data management plan</i>	<i>due in M6</i>
<i>D1.3</i>	<i>Ethics & Privacy management plan</i>	<i>due in M6</i>
<i>D2.1</i>	<i>Joint internationalization strategy for R&I</i>	<i>due in M18</i>
<i>D2.2</i>	<i>Report on networks analysis</i>	<i>due in M8</i>
<i>D3.1</i>	<i>Human resources strategy</i>	<i>due in M27</i>
<i>D3.2</i>	<i>Report on job shadowing and training of researcher managers</i>	<i>due in M27</i>
<i>D4.1</i>	<i>Report on RM strategy implementation</i>	<i>due in M36</i>
<i>D4.2</i>	<i>Policy recommendations for synergies among research funding programs</i>	<i>due in M36</i>
<i>D5.1</i>	<i>Plan for the dissemination and exploitation of results including communication activities</i>	<i>due in M6</i>

7. Planning, Monitoring and Data protection

7.1 Data usage

In line with the framework program’s rules on research data management, the consortium will develop a **Data Management Plan** with a deliverable in M6. The Data Management Plan will be updated accordingly in M15 and M36. The Data Management Plan will exist as a living document, respecting the rules for open science in the Horizon Europe program.

Even though this project does not entail to use any ethically sensitive tools such as AI or similar, the coordinator will ensure the compliance with ethics and GDPR requirements through creating an **Ethics & Privacy Management Plan** (also as a deliverable in M6).

7.2 Key Performance Indicators

The project’s communication, dissemination and exploitation activities will be undertaken according to the following key performance indicators (KPIs). They will **guide the monitoring and evaluation of the project’s performance and outreach** in regard to online media, press coverage, and events. A database was created and available to all partners to register and keep track of these activities.

Table 3 RIS4SEB’s Key Performance Indicators

Category	KPI	Value	KPI responsibility	Monitoring mechanism
National and regional Managing Authorities	# of representatives directly involved in the Advisory Board	7	VSE	Invitation emails, social media invites
EU Institutions (DG Region, DG RTD)	# of representatives directly involved in the Advisory Board	2	VSE	Invitation emails, social media invites
Associations of Universities and Businesses (in widening countries)	# of associations addressed as dissemination multipliers	4	VSE and KTU	Direct emails, social media invites
EARMA and CZARMA	# of Research Management professional associations involved in international dissemination action towards the community of research managers and administrators.	2	VSE	D5.3 EARMA conference
Representatives of Economics and Business Schools in widening countries	# of Economics and Business universities or schools involved in the community	30	KTU	Conference participants report
Networks of National Contact Points in widening countries	# of National Contact Point networks involved as dissemination multipliers	3 (1 for each widening partner country)	VSE, KTU, and EBS	Direct emails / invites
Other projects funded under the pilot	# of “sister” projects addressed to provide mutual	20	VSE	Direct emails / invites

<i>Pathways to synergies call</i>	<i>feedback and serve as information multipliers</i>			
<i>Project website</i>	<i># of websites</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>VSE</i>	<i>Website link</i>
<i>Direct contacts with identified target groups</i>	<i># of direct contacts</i>	<i>100</i>	<i>KTU</i>	<i>Conference participants report</i>
<i>Publication of project results and policy recommendations in trusted repositories</i>	<i># of policy recommendation papers</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>VSE</i>	<i>Zenodo uploads</i>
	<i># of downloads of the project results</i>	<i>500</i>	<i>VSE</i>	<i>Zenodo uploads</i>
<i>Final conference</i>	<i># of conferences</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>KTU</i>	<i>Conference report</i>
<i>Implementation and piloting of new strategies</i>	<i># of new strategies implemented and piloted during project duration</i>	<i>3 for each partner</i>	<i>Every partner</i>	<i>Feedback report</i>
<i>Social media presence</i>	<i># of social media channels developed</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>VSE</i>	<i>X and LinkedIn profile link</i>
<i>LinkedIn community engagement</i>	<i># of people involved through the LinkedIn community</i>	<i>1000</i>	<i>VSE</i>	<i>LinkedIn report as a part of PEDR</i>
<i>Public media outputs</i>	<i># of public media outputs</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>VSE</i>	<i>Press releases as a part of PEDR</i>

Conclusion

The Plan for the dissemination and exploitation of results is the key document to guide the project's activities in a strategic way. It aims to support consortium members in communication, dissemination and exploitation activities by giving guidelines to identify relevant target groups and key messages, follow the project identity guidelines, use consistently the dissemination and communication tools and channels, gain a broader view of community building and engagement, and finally keep in mind planning and monitoring mechanisms.

The Plan is in line with Article 17 of the Horizon Europe Grant Agreements' "the beneficiaries must promote the action and its results by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public) and in a strategic, coherent and effective manner."